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SARAJEVO

FACULTY OF
TECHNOLOGY
ZVORNIK

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ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT
AND MATERIALS IN
PROCESSING INDUSTRY

PROCEEDINGS

JAHORINA
11th - 13th March 2019

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BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY ZVORNIK**

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**“ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN
PROCESSING INDUSTRY”**

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SENSORY PROPERTIES OF BREAD WITH ADDITION OF ROSE HIP BY-PRODUCT

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Abstract

*Functional food is food whose biological characteristics have a positive impact on our health and certain body functions. The aim of this paper is to examine the possibility of using a rose hip by-product as an additive that would provide good product quality with improving functional and nutritive values. Its impact has been determined based upon finished product quality. A by-product from the production of herbal filter tea from *Rosa canina* L., by local tea manufacturer "Fructus" Backa Palanka, was used as herbal material. Bread quality was graded sensory 24h after baking, whereby the fineness of the crumb pore structure and elasticity were evaluated. We can conclude that the bread made in this way has significantly enriched content. Considering the previously described rose hip chemical composition and the report that this fruit contains very significant phytonutrients, such as tocopherols, phenolic compounds, carotenoids, sugars, organic acids, essential fatty acids and fruit acids, it can be concluded that even the smallest amounts of these substances that remain in bread products and bakery products are important.*

Key words: *rose hip, by-product, additive, functional bread*

Introduction

Functional food is food whose biological characteristics have a positive impact on our health and certain body functions. In its form it is similar to conventional food that represents part of our usual nutrition, but has psychophysical advantages aside from the basic nutritive functions. It can improve the general state of organism, decrease the risk from various diseases as well as help in treating some illnesses (Menrad, 2003; Mark-Herbert, 2004). In most cases functional food contains nutraceuticals, products that can be found in various forms, whether as a pure concentrated nutrient, food supplement, herbal product or natural plant component (Kajla et al., 2014).

Examples for each of these food types can be found on the market: beta carotene from carrot, fruits and vegetables, lutein, lycopene, dietary fibers (barley, oats, wheat bran), Omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins and antioxidants, phytoestrogens from soya and soya products, flavonoids and other substances in fruit/citruses and vegetables, probiotics, prebiotics and calcium from yoghurt and other dairy products, as well as other (Kajla et al., 2014).

Functional food technology is increasingly developing as an answer to consumer demands to improve their nutrition and use certain health benefits that the functional components provide (Kajla et al., 2014). Considering the large presence of bread and baking products in the daily meal structure, in this experimental work emphasis is on bread making. In the raw material content of different types of bread there are no significant differences when it comes to basic raw

materials, but the differences are evident when it comes to additional materials and additives. In baking products technology additional raw materials play a role in modifying flour quality (additives in baking industry), achieving functional product characteristics and improving its nutritive values (Šoronja-Simović, 2012).

The aim of this paper is to examine the possibility of using a rose hip by-product as an additive that would provide good product quality with improving functional and nutritive values. Its impact has been determined based upon finished product quality.

Material and methods

For analysing the possibility of using rose hip herbal dust for the production of bread with improved properties, flour for sour pastries and home-made pasta T-500, manufactured by "Danubius doo" from Novi Sad, was used.

Other raw materials used in this experiment are:

- Salt, commercial product, manufactured by "Kristal" D.O.O., Belgrade,
- Fresh bakers' yeast, manufactured by "Vrenje" from Belgrade
- Commercial additive "Blue tiger" D.O.O., Puratos, Kragujevac,
- Tap water.

A by-product from the production of herbal filter tea from *Rosa canina* L., by local tea manufacturer "Fructus" Backa Palanka, was used as herbal material. Different technological operations such as drying, grinding, sifting, mixing, etc. are used in the production of tea, where a certain amount of fine plant powder (about 20%) is created, which is often called herbal dust (Ramić et al., 2015). This fraction cannot be used to pack filter tea bags since its particle diameter is smaller than the size of the bag's pores (<0.315 mm). Therefore, this fraction is discarded from production as a by-product. Although in filter tea production there is a certain degradation of bioactive compounds relative to the starting plant material (Vidović et al., 2013), this by-product still contains a significant amount of high-value compounds.

As a herbal drug, the most important is rose hip fruit (*Cynosbati fructus*) (Ozcan, 2002). The official drug is *Rosae pseudofructus* (Ph Eur 7.0), represented by a receptacle and the remains of dried cup leaves with removed ahenies. Fresh, ripe fruit is used in the food industry as a raw material for the production of jam, marmalade, juice, vitamin concentrates, extracts, etc. (Ercisli, 2007; Zhang et al., 2008, Guimaraes et al., 2010). Lately it is also used as an ingredient in probiotic beverages, various types of yoghurts and soups (Demir et al., 2014).

In terms of chemical composition, rose hip fruit is characterized as raw material with high content of phytonutrients (Ercisli, 2007; Baros et al., 2011; Mishan et al., 2013; Demir et al., 2014) such as: Vitamin C, phenolic compounds, carotenoids, chlorophylls, essential fatty acids and tocopherols, fruit acids, pectins and other compounds. In general, this plant is considered to be a significant natural source of vitamin C (Erenturk et al., 2005; Kobus et al., 2005; Novak, 2006), and according to the requirements of Ph Eur 7.0 the rose hip fruit should contain at least 0.3% of this substance. The dominant phenolic compounds in the rose hip fruit are flavonoids, quercetin and kaempferol and their derivatives (Gao et al., 2000; Hvattum, 2002; Novak, 2006; Adamczak, 2012; Mikulic-Petkovsek et al., 2012). Carotenoids are significantly present in rose hip fruit, and as the most widely present β -carotene, lycopene, rubixanthin, zeaxanthin and lutein (Hodisan et al., 1997; Innocenti, 2004; Fan et al., 2014;). These compounds have a wide structural diversity and numerous biological functions such as macular degeneration prevention, cataracts, atherosclerosis and some types of cancer (Ganguly et al. ., 1980; Liand & Tan, 1994; Lu et al., 2005; Macias-Sanchez et al., 2010). One of the most important components of this

plant is fatty oil rich in vitamin E, and is present in the amount from 2 to 10% (Wichtl, 2002; PDR, 2007; Chrubasik et al., 2008). In addition, oil is a significant source of unsaturated fatty acids, out of which the most common is linoleic (35.9-54.8%), then α -linolenic (16.6-26.5%) and oleic acid (14.7-22.1%) (Zlatanov, 1999; Ozcan, 2002; Szentmihályi et al., 2002; Ilyasoglu, 2014; Helbig et al., 2008;). As already mentioned rose hip fruit contains other compounds such as ascorbic acid, but it also contains a large number of different chemical compounds, including pectins, tannins and fruit acids (Tylor, 1993; Ziegler et al., 1986). Furthermore, monosaccharides/oligosaccharides, amino acids, mineral substances (Ercisli, 2007; Baros et al., 2011; Mishan et al., 2013, Demir et al., 2014,) are also present. Sugars present in rose hip fruit are invert sugar and saccharose and from mineral substances phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, copper, manganese and zinc (Ercisli, 2007).

Due to the significant phytonutrients found in rose hip fruit, it has been proven that this plant possesses a wide range of biological effects such as: anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiproliferative, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, anticancer effect, in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, arthritis therapy, as well as in cosmetics and cosmetic preparations (Chahoud et al., 2004; Ozkan et al., 2004; Chrubasik et al., 2008; Egea et al., 2010; Baros et al., 2011; Bremmer et al., 2011; Tumbas et al., 2012; Guimaraes et al., 2014; Grayer et al., 2015; Oyedemi et al., 2016;).

Bread-making process with and without adding rose hip

Dough ingredients were as follows: flour 300gr, salt 2% (compared to flour mass), yeast 2.5% (compared to flour mass). Additional materials are mixed according to the experiment plan whereby part of the flour was exchanged with rose hip fruit herbal dust (Table 1).

Table 1. Experiment plan

Sample	Rose hip (%compared to flour mass)	Additive (%compared to flour mass)
1	0	0
2	0	0.2
3	0	0.4
4	5	0
5	5	0.2
6	5	0.4
7	10	0
8	10	0.2
9	10	0.4

According to the mentioned experiment plan the dough was mixed in Brabender's farinograph. After mass fermentation at 30°C in a thermostat chamber, the dough pieces were roundly shaped and left for 10 minutes on the work area (intermediary fermentation). Afterwards the dough was linear shaped and put into greased bread molds. The final fermentation was at 30°C for around 60 minutes. The end of the final fermentation was determined based on experience. Bread samples were baked in the laboratory oven produced by Chopin for around 20 minutes at 250°C.

Determining bread quality with the addition of rose hip fruit herbal dust

Bread quality was graded 24h after baking, whereby the fineness of the crumb pore structure and elasticity were evaluated. Descriptive grades of mentioned bread crumb quality indicators are shown in total values and graded in table for grading the bread crumb value (Kaluderski and Filipović, 1998) and marked as Value for Bread Crumb – VBC (minimum 0.0 maximum 7.0). The volume of the finished product is determined by volumetre filled with millet, using the squeezing method (AACC, 2000).

Results and Discussion

Bread-making and evaluating bread quality

Changing bread quality in terms of independently chosen parameters was determined based on acquired results shown in table 2.

Table 2. Evaluating bread quality (mean values per sample), with mean values of Value for Bread Crumb – VBC

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Bread mass (gr)	133.21	134.48	134.29	137.19	132.14	133.69	136.64	135.65	136.46
Bread mass after 24h (gr)	124.62	125.20	126.14	127.18	125.24	126.20	129.71	126.56	124.36
Bread volume (ml)	215	245	235	225	210	245	220	235	270
Bread height (mm)	76.5	87.5	85.5	71.0	80.5	85.0	71.5	83.5	86.0
Crumb elasticity	Very good - (3.8)	Very good + (4.2)	Very good (4.0)	Satisfactory (2.0)	Very good (4.0)	Very good / good (3.5)	Good (3.0)	Good + (3.2)	Excellent (4.5)
Pore structure fineness	Little rough/rough (0.8)	Almost fine / little rough (1.2)	Little rough + (1.1)	Rough (0.5)	Little rough + (1.1)	Almost fine / little rough (1.2)	Rough (0.5)	Almost fine / little rough (1.2)	Almost fine / little rough (1.2)
VBC	4.6	5.4	5.1	2.5	5.1	4.7	3.5	4.4	5.7

For each sample 2 pieces of bread were baked and the bread mass values were measured after baking, then after 24h, as well as volume and height values shown as average values of acquired results.

In order to understand bread quality values easier, after baking bread samples without the addition of rose hip, and with the addition of 5% and 10% rose hip, all three samples were photographed, as well as their cross sections, so a difference in appearance between the samples can be clearly seen (Figure 1).

Fig.1. Exterior appearance (A) and cross section appearance (B) bread samples without rose hip addition, with 5 and 10% rose hip addition

In Fig.1.A the external appearance of bread samples is shown made from flour without rose hip (left), then bread made with 5% added rose hip (in the middle), and bread made from flour with 10% rose hip addition (right). In Fig.1.B the cross section of the same samples is shown. All photographed samples were made without adding additives. What is evident and clearly noticeable with the naked eye is the difference in appearance between the samples (crust colour, crumb colour, texture). Other changes in quality are valued using defined methods and are given in the rest of the paper.

Impact of adding rose hip on the quality of the finished product

As already mentioned table 2 shows results of evaluating bread quality. Analyzing results acquired from examining dough made from flour, without additives (sample 1), with 0.2% additives (sample 2) and 0.4% additives (sample 3), it can be concluded that the bread quality was significantly improved by adding a small amount of additives (0.2%). Bread volume, as well as, height obviously increase, and as a confirmation of improved bread quality values for crumb elasticity and pore structure fineness were determined. A clear indicator is the VBC value which is obtained by a sum of their values, and for sample 2 with the addition of 0.2% additives it is 5.4. For sample 3 where 0.4% additives were added to basic dough, the bread volume and height values were lower, but that can be explained with the shorter time interval of final fermentation.

When rose hip was added to basic dough in the concentration of 5% compared to the flour mass (samples 4-6) with the change of other parameters (using additives) the following results were acquired: Bread sample with 5% rose hip addition (sample 4) had low height and lower value of VBC. With the small addition of additives (0.2%) (sample 5), bread quality improved significantly. Bread height increased for 14.3%. VBC value was very high (5.1). When a larger amount of additives was added to the sample values of mass, volume and height of attained bread increased, but values for crumb elasticity and structure fineness were somewhat lower. Generally, sensory bread characteristics were graded with the grade very good. Bread colour was as expected light pink due to the colour substances present in the rose hip fruit. Smell and taste of bread were pleasant and balanced.

When it comes to bread samples with a higher amount of added rose hip (10%), based upon the acquired results it was determined that the addition of additives has a positive impact on the tested bread quality parameters. The sample with the higher added amount of additives (0.4%) had better bread quality (bread volume 270 ml, bread height 86mm, excellent crumb elasticity, pore structure fineness 1.2). This can be explained by the fact that rose hip seeds contain a significant amount of fatty oil (up to 10%) (Chrubasik et al., 2008), and thus a larger amount of additives is necessary for dough rising. Also, oil improves the elasticity of bread crumb so the attained VBC value is exceptionally high 5.7, therefore it can be concluded that the made bread is of high quality. Smell and taste of bread sample with the addition of 10% rose hip, did not significantly differ from bread samples with 5% rose hip addition. However, 10% rose hip addition significantly influenced the change of bread taste which manifested in characteristic mild sourly but still pleasant taste. Results of sensory bread quality testing showed that a product attained in this way is of acceptable good quality, which makes working with such samples highly justified.

Conclusions

If we go back to the characteristics and importance of rose hip fruit as an added raw material, we can conclude that the bread made in this way has significantly enriched content. Considering the previously described rose hip chemical composition and the report that this fruit contains very significant phytonutrients, such as tocopherols, phenolic compounds, carotenoids, sugars, organic acids, essential fatty acids and fruit acids, it can be concluded that even the smallest amounts of these substances that remain in bread products and bakery products are of extreme

importance. Thus, it clearly shows that these types of products enriched with the addition of rose hip by-product, under examined terms, represent functional food and can be an important part of our nutrition.

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